

Name: Aryan Nava

Title: Founder | Chief Strategy Officer | Blockchain Mind Inc

TOPIC TITLE: DO IT YOURSELF ICO (DIY ICO) under \$100K

INTRODUCTION:

Founder and Chief Business Development officer of Blockchain Mind Inc . He is an IT technology Entrepreneur, Stocks Advisor at [Vetr](#) (crowdsourced stock rating site) and having over 13,000 followers. He had been contributing to his technical blog ([AryanNava](#)) for last 10 years and over 1.2 million views so far with 2000 followers. He is currently working on smart contract development, setting up workshop to educate general public about cryptocurrency trading, Setting up private Blockchain, Developing supply chain Blockchain platform & Helping clients to launch ICO (Initial Coin Offerings) on Ethereum & building smart parking using Blockchain and Hardware wallet.

BIOGRAPHY:

I worked in the Big Data/Data Analytics/Middleware/Storage sector for the last 18+ years for corporations like Toronto Stock Exchange, Canadian Depository for Securities, TSX Venture Exchange, **TSX Trust, Economical Insurance, Extendicare, Direct Energy and E-health Ontario and Lehman Brothers**

I have a background in Big Data, Cloud, IT Security, Sales, Channel Management, Start-ups, technical/business skills regarding blockchain, Crypto Currencies, Initial Coin Offering and a good network of contacts in Tech/Finance sectors in Toronto, New York, Bay Area and Bangalore.